

spikelet sterility. In the BC₅ also, pollen and spikelet sterility were maintained in the progenies. The CMS line derived from progeny 1 was named Pusa 5A.

The outcrossing potential of this line was evaluated against IR58025 A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10A using the respective B lines. Pusa 5A recorded a seed yield of 2.8 t ha⁻¹ vs 2.0, 0.6, 0.7, and 0.8 t ha⁻¹ of IR58025A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10 A, respectively. Pusa 5A had more tillers, longer panicles, more spikelets panicle⁻¹, and better stigma exertion than IR58025A. Pusa 5A may therefore prove to be a good alternative to IR58025A, the most popular cytoplasmic male sterile line used in India. ■

Field evaluation of thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines

C.H.M. Vijayakumar, M.Ilyas-Ahmed, B.C. Viraktamath, M.S. Ramesha, and S. Singh, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

The use of thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) is well recognized in two-line heterosis breeding. The use of the TGMS system has several advantages over the cytoplasmic genic male sterility system, such as (1) its simple and efficient seed production system, and (2) its greater scope for enhancing heterosis because any genotype can be used as a male parent. To develop hybrids using the TGMS system, it is necessary to identify or develop lines that show a desirable transformation from fertility to sterility and vice versa.

We evaluated several TGMS lines that carried TGMS genes introduced from IRRI. Besides intensive study under field conditions for five seasons, starting in 1994, we made simultaneous individual plant selections in these lines. The TGMS lines were (1) IR68945-4-33-14, (2) IR68948-12-3-7, (3) IR68949-11-5-31, (4) IR68945-4-33-4-14, and (5) IR32364-120-1-3-2. Lines 1, 2, and 3 showed very good transformation between seasons. At Hyderabad,

during the wet season, the weather is unstable and daily mean temperatures below 25 °C occur frequently. The daily maximum temperature is 29 °C, which induces fertility in most of the IRRI-bred TGMS lines. During the dry season, however, the daily mean temperature is always >25 °C, with a daily maximum of >32 °C beginning in the second week of March, which induces sterility in most lines, including the selected lines 1, 2, 3, and 4.

During the 1995-96 dry season, 325 plant progenies of TGMS lines 1, 2, 3, and 4 were evaluated in two sets planted at 10-d intervals. The results showed that IR68945-4-33-14 still segregated for plant type, grain type, and sterility, whereas IR68948-12-3-7 and IR68949-11-5-31 were almost stable. Another line, IR68945-4-33-4-14, was uniform, but partially fertile, and appeared to be a very high-temperature sterile type. Plants showing stable sterility were selected and their stubble was planted in the 1996 wet season, in which all those lines transformed to fertility further confirmed their behavior. IR32364-120-1-3-2 did not set seeds in either season after 1994. Although the anthers were light yellow, they did not shed any pollen, which was >99% abortive type. Perhaps it is a very low-temperature fertile type. Lines IR68948-12-3-7 and IR68949-11-5-31, which also have desirable floral traits that influence outcrossing, will be used in hybrid rice breeding in the coming years. ■

Developing thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

K. Thiyagarajan, P. Jayamani, R. Latha, P. Suthamathi, and M. Rangaswamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

The three-line method (A/B/R) of heterosis breeding is cumbersome and warrants development of alternate approaches to exploit hybrid vigor commercially in rice. Two-line breeding

is one such possibility that emerged following the chance discovery of photoperiod-sensitive genic sterile (PGMS) lines and thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines in China.

A study was conducted to identify a stable TGMS source from suspected and introduced TGMS lines under natural conditions. Thirty-eight lines were evaluated at Coimbatore (high temperature 38/23 °C) and at Gudalur (low temperature 30/16 °C) simultaneously during summer 1995. Pollen fertility in these lines was recorded during the flowering stage using I-KI (1%) solution. Panicles were bagged and spikelet fertility recorded.

Lines TS 15 and TS 16 showed 100% pollen sterility at Coimbatore and 55-80% pollen fertility at Gudalur. The sterile lines are maintained as stubble at Coimbatore for further evaluation in the wet season. These lines are also evaluated under controlled conditions to determine the critical sterility and fertility points of temperature. Crosses are also made simultaneously with agronomically superior lines to transfer the TGMS genes. ■

Male sterility and fertility behavior of suspected thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines

C.R. Elsy and M. Rangaswamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

The male sterility-fertility response in thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was studied to identify their adaptability to different temperature regimes. Twenty suspected TGMS lines available at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, were used for the study. The plants of these lines, which were completely male sterile during summer 1995, were tagged and observed for their male sterility-fertility behavior in the ratooned tillers during winter 1995 and summer 1996 by staining pollen grains with I-KI. Panicle development stages, from the